

Factors Affecting The Efficiency Implementation For New Rural Programs: A Case Study Of Suburban Districts In Ho Chi Minh City

Bui Hong Trang, Nga Phan Thi Hang

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Efficient, Implementation, Rural, Programs, HCMC, UFM</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5228406</p>	<p><i>Nowadays, the new rural development program transforms the rural economic structure and restructures the agricultural sector. Besides, the rural areas have achieved many remarkable achievements. It continues creating a significant turning point in rural development. Moreover, the new rural construction program contributes to increasing the satisfaction with rural residents' lives, creating a foundation for socio-political stability through rising incomes and reducing rural poverty. Therefore, the authors surveyed 550 residents living in suburban districts of Ho Chi Minh City. The article finds out the key factors affecting the efficient implementation of new rural programs with 1% significance. The authors applied structural equation modeling (SEM). Finally, the authors had policy recommendations to improve the efficient implementation of new rural programs of suburban districts in Ho Chi Minh City.</i></p>

INTRODUCTION

There is building a new countryside, rural people's material and spiritual life is rich and prosperous, approaching the urban area; rural socio-economic infrastructure is synchronous (Martens, P. (2015)). In 2025, there are at least 15 provinces recognized by the Prime Minister to complete the task of building new rural areas (Northern mountainous region: 01 province, Red River Delta: 08 provinces, North Central: 01 province, South Central: 01 province, Central Highlands: 01 province; Southeast: 04 provinces, Mekong Delta: 04 provinces). At the district level, the whole country has 40% of districts, towns, and cities directly under the province to complete the task of building new rural areas (Northern Mountains: 20%, Red River Delta: 80%, North Central: 30%, South Central Coast: 30%, Central Highlands: 20%; Southeast: 70%, Mekong River Delta: 35%).

Each province and city directly under the Central Government has at least 02 district-level units meeting the standards. New countryside; at least 10% of districts meet the criteria recognized as newly enhanced and model rural districts. At the commune level, 80% of communes meet new rural standards (Northern Mountain: 60%, Red River Delta: 99%, North Central: 87%, South Central: 80%, Central Highlands: 68%; East Southern region: 95%, Mekong River Delta: 80%), of which at least 30% of communes meet the new advanced rural standards, 10% of the communes meet the model-new rural standards; there are no communes under ten criteria according to the national set of criteria for new rural areas in the period of 2021-2025.

At the village level, 80% of villages, hamlets, and hamlets in extremely difficult communes in border areas, mountainous areas, coastal flat areas, and islands are recognized as meeting new rural standards according to newly applied rural criteria at village level according to regulations. The quality of life of rural residents is improved, the average income increases at least 1.8 times compared to 2020. Moreover, the article finds out the key factors affecting the efficient implementation of new rural programs in suburban districts of Ho Chi Minh City.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The efficiency implementation for new rural programs (HQCTNTM)

Madu, I. A. (2017) showed that new rural construction is the process of transforming and creating new values for rural areas in terms of political security, economy, culture, and modern production methods. The process of implementing the National Criteria for New Rural areas has shown difficulties and obstacles in management and monitoring, measurement, and evaluation of results. The National Target Program's effectiveness on building new rural areas in the next period is necessary to continue researching and adjusting the National Criteria for new rural areas accordingly, creating measurement standards for rural areas. New rural construction results by Decision No. 1980/QĐ-TTg dated (2016).

The new countryside is the transformation of the rural face based on preserving and promoting progressive values and achievements, building new deals in line with the trend of the times, meeting established criteria suggestion. The Party and State have always paid agriculture and rural development special attention. The document of the 10th National Congress of the Party has determined: “Completely formulate agricultural and rural development plannings by Decision No. 491/QD-TTg dated (2013). Implement the new rural construction program to build villages, communes, hamlets, and hamlets with a prosperous, civilized, clean and beautiful life associated with the formation of urbanized residential areas. They were promoting democracy, building a cultural lifestyle, eliminating social evils in the countryside.

Infrastructure (CSHT)

Hoggart, K., & H. (2019) argued that In the National Target Program for New Rural Development, planning and infrastructure construction criteria play a crucial role in creating the foundation for implementing the remaining standards. Build a new rural area with a step-by-step modern socio-economic infrastructure has focused its resources on investing in transportation, irrigation, schools, healthcare, and agricultural development. Industry and services; to associate rural development with urbanization, gradually meeting the people’s production and daily-life requirements (2010). Thanks to the effective investment and use of the infrastructural works related to the construction of new homes, the material and spiritual life of the people significantly improved by Mitrokostas, E. (2017). The rate of poor households decreased, an average annual decrease; per capita income reached more than last year. The grassroots medical stations are invested, renovated, upgraded, and purchased with all necessary equipment to meet medical examination and treatment needs. Based on the concept mentioned above and studies, the authors gave hypothesis H1 following:

Hypothesis H1: Infrastructure (CSHT) positively impacts the efficient implementation of new rural programs in suburban districts of Ho Chi Minh City.

Economic - Social (KTXH)

Ramos, K. B. (2019) studied that develop socio-economic infrastructure, basically synchronously, ensures rural-urban connectivity and regional connectivity. The rural infrastructure facilities of urban areas and big cities must have higher requirements (in terms of technique, scale, content, art...) compared to other regions, ensuring synchronous connectivity with urban at the same time by Decision No. 491/QD-TTg dated (2013). Economic - Social is a set of synchronous objectives such as economy, social, technology, and environment. Its’ tasks have many solutions to improve mechanisms, policies, and laws. Besides, Economic - Social has several objectives identified in the national. There are development planning of the industry or field for a specific time by Government, Resolution (2008). Based on the concept mentioned above and studies, the authors gave hypothesis H2 following:

Hypothesis H2: Economic - Social (KTXH) positively impacts the efficient implementation of new rural programs in suburban districts of Ho Chi Minh City.

Organization of production (TCSX)

Trogu, D. M. (2015) showed that to develop production, sustainably raise people’s income, and respond to climate change, focusing on exploiting the advantages of each region and region. To focus on accelerating the implementation of agricultural restructuring, renewing the growth model associated with the development of clean agriculture, organic agriculture, and high-tech agriculture following actual conditions. Besides, the production organization successfully converts inefficient rice-growing land to produce other more efficient crops and animals. Building large-scale concentrated agricultural raw material areas associated with growing area codes, product barcodes, meeting quality management standards (VietGap, GlobalGap), and traceability for all agricultural products by Nguyen Van Bich (2000).

Cena, D. F. (2014) showed that taking advantage of topographical conditions, climate, natural landscape, and socio-economic infrastructure promotes tourism economic development, focusing on rural tourism and eco-tourism models. associated with promoting the development of traditional OCOP products... Paying attention to afforestation, forest protection, and sustainable forestry development; develop models of growing medicinal plants under the forest canopy, especially regional specialties with high economic value.

Vaishar, A. (2019) showed that the developing production links along the value chain strengthen the preservation and processing of agricultural products, forming a system of centers to connect, promote consumption, and export products associated with a chain of wholesale markets or centers for supplying agricultural products. Continue to effectively implement the One Commune One Product Program to diversify and further improve the quality associated with brand building, creating favorable conditions for product consumption and export. Create more preferential mechanisms and policies to attract large enterprises to invest in the processing sector. This factor increases the added value of products such as product consumption and

non-agricultural sectors to create more jobs for laborers by Cena, D. F. (2014). Based on the concepts mentioned earlier and studies, authors gave hypothesis H3 following:

Hypothesis H3: Organization of production (TCSX) positively impacts the efficient implementation of new rural programs in suburban districts of Ho Chi Minh City.

Culture - Social - Environment (VHXHMT)

According to Boncinelli, F. (2017), protect the environment and improve the rural landscape. Leaders must pay this factor to environmental protection in rural areas (increasing the proportion of solid waste, domestic wastewater, packaging of plant protection drugs classified, collected, and treated). Besides, attract large enterprises to invest in centralized waste treatment zones of inter-district and inter-provincial scale, and at the same time encourage the development of household and village-scale domestic wastewater treatment models in residential communities.

Leaders continue to launch and maintain movements to say no to plastic waste and reuse agricultural waste to ensure compliance with environmental hygiene regulations and food safety regulations. Besides, improve the ecological landscape; focus on developing models of green, clean, and beautiful villages and hamlets as a premise for rural tourism development in the province in the long run. To step up environmental treatment in places causing severe pollution (craft villages, concentrated landfills, garbage, and wastewater treatment.) by Communist Party of Vietnam (2006). Develop education, health care, grassroots culture and preserve and promote traditional cultural values associated with the economic development of rural tourism; Maintain security and social order in rural areas by Michalek, J., & Zarnekow, N. (2012) and Dagevos H., G.(2018). Based on the concepts mentioned above and studies, authors gave hypothesis H4 following:

Hypothesis H4: Culture - Social - Environment (VHXHMT) positively impacts the efficient implementation of new rural programs in suburban districts of Ho Chi Minh City.

Political system (HTCT)

According to Wook, M. K. (2017), the whole political system joins hands with the people to build a new countryside. Improve the quality of Party building work, effectiveness and efficiency of operations, and government administration at all levels. Renovate the Fatherland front and mass organizations; strengthen supervision and social criticism. Continue to promote the spirit of solidarity, unity, discipline, discipline, order, and working style among the leaders, cadres, and party members to build a solid political system and resolve to complete the task. Fulfill all the political functions of the locality by Zantyley, V. T. (2019). The view that building a new countryside is the task of both the political system and the whole society; Party committees and authorities play the role of leading, directing and administering, organizing the implementation, and motivating the people to promote their role as the subject of new rural construction. Resolution No. 06-NQ/TU on implementing the National Target Program on building a pristine countryside in the province. Based on the concept mentioned above and studies, the authors gave hypothesis H5 following:

Hypothesis H5: Political system (HTCT) positively impacts the efficient implementation of new rural programs in suburban districts of Ho Chi Minh City.

The authors had a research model and the hypothesis following:

(Source: Authorsproposed)

Figure 1. The research model for factors affecting the efficient implementation of new rural programs of suburban districts in Ho Chi Minh City

METHODS OF RESEARCH

The research method of the topic is a combination of qualitative research methods and quantitative research methods.

(Source: Authors proposed)

Figure 2. The research process for factors affecting the efficient implementation of new rural programs of suburban districts in Ho Chi Minh City

Authors using mixed qualitative and quantitative research methods. The authors used qualitative research to interview four experts in-depth. They discussed with six members to determine the research model and scale - quantitative analysis to assess the influence of factors.

The authors' sampling method is non-probability, convenient. Sample size, the author applied according to Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., & Black, W. (2010) with $n > 5 * \text{total number of observed variables}$. In the questionnaire, there are 26 observed variables, so $n > 5 * 26 = 130$. To ensure the reliability of the research, the author issued 550 votes and collected 525 valid votes for testing. The authors using SPSS 20.0 software by Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., & Black, W. (2010).

Quantitative research: Qualitative research includes interviewing ten experts (4 experts in-depth and discuss with six members). Qualitative research results gave the authors lots of authentic, valuable information about the efficient implementation of new rural programs of suburban districts in Ho Chi Minh City. The article also combines practice and a theoretical basis to propose research models and hypotheses. The observed variables were built on previous studies and corrected contributions by ten experts Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., and Black, W. (2010).

The quantitative study was conducted with an expected sample size of $n = 550$ persons living in suburban districts of Ho Chi Minh City. The authors used a convenient sampling method to pick a sample, but 525 samples were processed, leaving 25 samples unprocessed. Moreover, testing the reliability of the independent variables all have Cronbach's Alpha > 0.6 , all observed variables have a total correlation > 0.3 . so, all of the variables are reliability tests. Thus, after testing the reliability of Cronbach's Alpha, the remaining five independent variables with 22 observed variables met the requirements for inclusion in exploratory factor analysis (EFA).

Next, 22 observed variables are grouped into five factors. The KMO measure (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) has a value > 0.6 , satisfying the condition of $0.5 \leq \text{KMO} \leq 1$, so the factor analysis is consistent with the actual and reliable data. The results of testing the correlation in each group of factors, Bartlett's Test has Sig value. = 0.000 < 0.05 means that the observed variables are correlated with each other in each factor group. The authors used SPSS 20.0 tools to measure Cronbach's Alpha's trust coefficient, EFA: explore factor analysis, confirmation factor analysis (CFA), and structural equation modeling (SEM) by Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., and Black, W. (2010).

RESEARCH RESULTS

Testing of Cronbach's alpha

Table 1. Testing of Cronbach's alpha for infrastructure (CSHT)

Code	Infrastructure (CSHT)	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
CSHT1	The planning for the development of socio-economic infrastructure in the locality announced to the people	0.851
CSHT2	Regulations on the management of communal construction planning promulgated and organized according to the planning	0.831
CSHT3	The current planning for the development of residential areas in the area ensures environmental sanitation	0.857
Cronbach's alpha: 0.892		

(Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0)

Table 1 showed that Cronbach's alpha for infrastructure (CSHT) meets this technique's requirements. Specifically, Cronbach's Alpha values of the infrastructure (CSHT) is 0.892, and Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted (>0.6).

Table 2. Testing of Cronbach's alpha for Economic - Social (KTXH)

Code	Economic - Social (KTXH)	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
KTXH1	Communal and inter-commune roads are asphalted or concreted to ensure convenient travel, and lanes are not muddy in the rainy season	0.941
KTXH2	The irrigation system meets the requirements of people's livelihood and production	0.955
KTXH3	The power system is supplied stably, regularly, and safely	0.951
KTXH4	Schools at all levels: preschool, kindergarten, primary school, and high school have national standard facilities and teaching equipment	0.933
KTXH5	Cultural houses, entertainment, and sports areas in the commune fully meet the daily needs of the people	0.940
Cronbach's alpha: 0.955		

(Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0)

Table 2 showed that Cronbach's alpha for the Economic - Social (KTXH) meets this technique's requirements. Specifically, Cronbach's Alpha values of the Economic - Social (KTXH) is 0.955, and Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted (>0.6).

Table 3. Testing of Cronbach's alpha for the organization of production (TCSX)

Code	Organization of production (TCSX)	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
TCSX1	Per capita income/year increased compared to the level before the implementation of the new rural program	0.885
TCSX2	The number of poor households decreased compared to before the implementation of the new rural program	0.926
TCSX3	The number of unemployed people has decreased since the implementation of the new rural program	0.929
TCSX4	The link between production and consumption of agricultural products is expanding	0.890
Cronbach's alpha: 0.929		

(Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0)

Table 3 showed that Cronbach's alpha for the organization of production (TCSX) meets this technique's requirements. Specifically, Cronbach's Alpha values of the organization of production (TCSX) is 0.929, and Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted (>0.6).

Table 4. Testing of Cronbach's alpha for Culture - Social - Environment (VHXHMT)

Code	Culture - Social - Environment (VHXHMT)	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
VHXHMT1	Children in the commune universalized from primary to high school	0.952
VHXHMT2	People can access medical facilities, dispensaries, hospitals and provide with essential medicines	0.961
VHXHMT3	The number of children under five years of age suffering from stunting had decreased compared to before the new rural program implemented	0.953
VHXHMT4	The number of households meeting the standard of cultural families increased when implementing the new rural program	0.948

VHXHMT5	People are allowed to use clean water and environmental sanitation when implementing the new rural program	0.954
VHXHMT6	Households, food production, and business establishments comply with regulations on ensuring food safety	0.949
Cronbach's alpha: 0.961		

(Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0)

Table 4 showed that Cronbach's alpha for the Culture - Social - Environment (VHXHMT) meets this technique's requirements. Specifically, Cronbach's Alpha values of the Culture - Social - Environment (VHXHMT) is 0.961, and Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted (>0.6).

Table 5. Testing of Cronbach's alpha for Political system (HTCT)

Code	Political system (HTCT)	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
HTCT1	Commune officials meet ethical standards, respect the people, and dedicate themselves to solving problems for the people	0.799
HTCT2	Professional capacity of commune officials to meet job requirements	0.794
HTCT3	Party committees, commune authorities meet the standard of "clean and strong"	0.821
HTCT4	Security and social order are maintained	0.783
Cronbach's alpha: 0.842		

(Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0)

Table 5 showed that Cronbach's alpha for the Political system (HTCT) meets this technique's requirements. Specifically, Cronbach's Alpha values of the Political system (HTCT) is 0.842, and Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted (>0.6).

Table 6. Testing of Cronbach's alpha for the efficient implementation for new rural programs (HQCTNTM)

Code	The efficiency implementation for new rural programs (HQCTNTM)	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
HQCTNTM1	The new rural program implemented to help the planning: Land, housing, transportation is better	0.849
HQCTNTM2	The new rural program implemented, bringing good infrastructure in the commune (electricity, water, cultural facilities.)	0.802
HQCTNTM3	A new rural program implemented to create jobs and increase people's income.	0.863
HQCTNTM4	The new rural program implemented to help people's living standards increased and people's intellectual level to be improved	0.804
Cronbach's alpha: 0.868		

(Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0)

Table 6 showed that Cronbach's alpha for the efficient implementation for new rural programs (HQCTNTM) meets this technique's requirements. Specifically, Cronbach's Alpha values of the efficient performance for new rural programs (HQCTNTM) is 0.868, and Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted (>0.6).

Table 7. Testing factors affecting the efficient implementation for new rural programs of suburban districts in Ho Chi Minh City

Relationships		Unstandardized Estimate	Standardized Estimate	S.E	C.R	P	Results
HQCTNTM	<--- VHXHMT	0.117	0.163	0.032	3.668	***	Accepted
HQCTNTM	<--- KTXH	0.078	0.115	0.027	2.880	0.004	Accepted
HQCTNTM	<--- TCSX	0.072	0.122	0.027	2.646	0.008	Accepted
HQCTNTM	<--- HTCT	0.083	0.115	0.030	2.716	0.007	Accepted
HQCTNTM	<--- CSHT	0.282	0.410	0.039	7.170	***	Accepted

(Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos)

Table 7 showed the factors affecting the efficient implementation of new rural programs of suburban districts in Ho Chi Minh City with a significance level of 0.01. These results are critical information for managerial implications to enhance the efficient implementation of new rural programs of suburban districts in Ho Chi Minh City for the following years. Besides, the research results are essential information for policymakers to refer to and apply in practice in rural areas of Vietnam.

Table 8. Testing Bootstrap with 50.000 samples for the efficient implementation of new rural programs of suburban districts in Ho Chi Minh City

Parameter	SE	SE-SE	Mean	Bias	SE-Bias
HQCTNTM <--- VHXHMT	0.033	0.000	0.114	-0.003	0.000
HQCTNTM <--- KTXH	0.028	0.000	0.077	-0.002	0.000
HQCTNTM <--- TCSX	0.033	0.000	0.073	0.001	0.000
HQCTNTM <--- HTCT	0.031	0.000	0.078	-0.005	0.000
HQCTNTM <--- CSHT	0.044	0.000	0.286	0.004	0.001

(Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos)

Table 9 showed that the bootstrap test results are very good with a sample of 50.000 persons living in new rural programs of suburban districts in Ho Chi Minh City. These results indicated five factors affecting the efficient implementation of new rural programs of suburban communities in Ho Chi Minh City with a significance level of 0.01.

(Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos)

Figure 3. Testing sem for five factors affecting the efficient implementation for new rural programs of suburban districts in Ho Chi Minh City

Figure 3 showed that the SEM assessment had five factors affecting the efficient implementation for new rural programs of suburban districts in Ho Chi Minh City with a significance level of 0.01. Figure 3 showed that the assessment of model index including: CMIN/DF = 3.474 (<5.0), GFI = 0.883 (>0.8), TLI = 0.940 (>0.9), CFI = 0.950 (> 0.9) and RMSE = 0.069 (<0.08). All model indicators showed five factors affecting the efficient implementation for new rural programs of suburban districts in Ho Chi Minh City with a significance level of 0.01.

CONCLUSION & POLICY IMPLICATIONS

Conclusion

The movement to build new rural areas has become a meaningful, humane, far-reaching movement, and the people have agreed to respond. People’s awareness about the construction of new rural areas is increasingly enhanced, especially in product development associated with product consumption linkages. They have the application of science - technology, environmental protection, rural landscape improvement, promote traditional cultural values, maintain security and order, contribute to change the face of the countryside fundamentally. This study’s main findings are all five factors affecting the efficient implementation of new rural programs of suburban districts in Ho Chi Minh City with a significance level of 0.01. Besides, the study found statistical evidence and a positive relationship with a significance level of 0.01. Based on the analysis results. The authors had policy recommendations to improve the efficient implementation of new rural programs in Ho Chi Minh City.

Policy implications

(1) Ho Chi Minh City should develop infrastructure, basically synchronously, to ensure rural-urban connectivity and regional connectivity. HCMC should continue to improve the quality of the basic infrastructure system in production and people's livelihood in rural areas. Besides, in the direction of meeting requirements and improving quality, focus on investing in building rural socio-economic infrastructure in association with urban development, gradually catching up with the general development speed of the region, creating synchronous connections, especially inter-communal and inter-communal connections. HCMC needs to expand and modernize the district-level central infrastructure system, focusing on developing and developing a plan to supply and connect modern agricultural products at the district level; proactively respond to natural disasters and climate change. The rural infrastructure facilities of urban areas and big cities must have higher requirements (in terms of technique, scale, content, art) than other areas, ensuring synchronous connectivity with urban at the same time.

(2) Ho Chi Minh City should develop and protect the environment and improve the rural landscape. HCMC must protect environmental problems in rural areas and encourage household and village-scale domestic wastewater treatment models in residential communities. Ho Chi Minh City should continue to launch and maintain movements to say no to plastic waste and reuse agricultural waste to ensure compliance with environmental hygiene regulations and food safety regulations. And improve the ecological landscape; focus on developing models of green, clean, and beautiful villages and hamlets as a premise for rural tourism development in the province in the long run. To step up environmental treatment in places causing severe pollution such as craft villages, concentrated landfills, garbage, and wastewater treatment.

(3) Ho Chi Minh City should develop production, sustainably raise people's income, and respond to climate change. To focus on exploiting the advantages of each region and region. Taking advantage of topographical conditions, climate, natural landscape, socio-economic infrastructure to promote tourism economic development, focusing on rural tourism, eco-tourism models. associated with promoting the development of traditional OCOP products...

Paying attention to afforestation, forest protection, and sustainable forestry development; develop models of growing medicinal plants under the forest canopy, especially regional specialties with high economic value. Develop production links along the value chain, strengthen the preservation and processing of agricultural products; forming a system of centers to connect, promote consumption, and export products associated with a chain of wholesale markets or centers for supplying agricultural products. Continue to effectively implement the One Commune One Product Program to diversify and further improve the quality associated with brand building, creating favorable conditions for product consumption and export. HCMC should promote production development, increase income. Continue to effectively implement the program on agricultural development with high technology application in association with agricultural restructuring. Strengthen trade promotion, support to find output markets for farm products.

(4) Ho Chi Minh City should develop education, health care, grassroots culture, preserve and promote traditional cultural values associated with the economic development of rural tourism, maintain security and social order in rural areas. Ho Chi Minh City should improve the quality of human resources for rural areas. Effectively implement the vocational training program for rural workers in association with the National Target Program on new rural construction. Vocational training must come from the needs of employers and society; at the same time, in line with the socio-economic development plan, production planning, and new rural construction planning of the locality. Content, programs, processes, and training methods for rural workers also need to be innovated to combine theory and practice. Diversify training methods and models, promote forms of association and coordination in training according to effective schemes, projects, and agricultural production models in the locality and through businesses with production-consumption association contracts with farmers. Focus on vocational training for rural youth, farmers directly engaged in agricultural production, poor households, near-poor households, people with disabilities, ethnic minorities, female workers, policy beneficiaries, and laborers in urbanized areas.

(5) Ho Chi Minh City should promote propaganda and awareness-raising for officials and rural residents, improve the quality of emulation movements to build new rural areas, and focus on enhancing the role of key players in rural development. HCMC strengthens the legal framework, mechanisms, and policies to support new rural construction to continue merging programs and projects with the same investment and support contents in rural areas. Besides, rural areas with the National Target Program on building new rural areas to unify mechanisms and policies to support localities to effectively implement the contents of the program, contributing to improving the efficiency of resource investment, ensuring no overlap, and wasting resources. Review, update and promulgate national criteria for new rural areas (village, village, commune, and district levels) suitable to each period. HCMC should promulgate a system of synchronous, flexible mechanisms and policies at all levels (province, district, commune, village). Besides, HCMC should enhance proper planning for each local group (striving to meet standards, having reached standards, striving for model achievement). Finally, HCMC promulgates the implementation plan of the movement "The whole country joins hands to build new countryside from 2021 through 2025," launched by the Prime Minister. Continue to

effectively implement the science and technology program in service of new rural construction from 2021 to 2025.

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Author Information

Bui Hong Trang

University of Finance - Marketing (UFM)

Nga Phan Thi Hang

University of Finance - Marketing (UFM)
